

AN ANALYTICAL STUDY ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED BANKING AND PSU DEBT MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The Indian mutual fund industry has witnessed substantial growth in recent years, particularly in debt-oriented schemes such as Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds. These funds primarily invest in debt securities issued by banks, public sector undertakings, and public financial institutions, offering comparatively lower risk and stable returns to investors. The present study titled "An Analytical Study on the Performance of Selected Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds in India" evaluates the performance of selected Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds namely, HDFC Banking and PSU Debt Fund, SBI Banking and PSU Debt Fund, Sundaram Banking & PSU Fund, and ICICI Prudential Banking & PSU Debt Fund during the period from 2021 to 2025. The study examines the risk-return relationship of the selected schemes using statistical and financial performance measures such as Annual Returns, Standard Deviation, Coefficient of Variation, Beta Coefficient, Sharpe Ratio, Treynor's Ratio, and Jensen's Alpha. The analysis reveals that Sundaram Banking & PSU Fund generated the highest average annual return with relatively lower volatility, whereas ICICI Prudential Banking & PSU Debt Fund demonstrated better stability in terms of systematic risk. HDFC Banking and PSU Debt Fund exhibited consistent performance across most evaluation parameters. The findings indicate that Banking and PSU Debt Funds provide comparatively stable investment opportunities during fluctuating market conditions and are suitable for conservative investors seeking regular income with moderate risk exposure. The study concludes that risk-adjusted performance measures are essential for evaluating mutual fund efficiency, as higher returns alone do not guarantee superior performance. The research contributes to investors, academicians, and financial analysts by providing insights into the comparative performance of debt mutual fund schemes in India and assisting investors in making informed investment decisions.

Keywords: Banking and PSU Debt Funds, Mutual Funds, Risk and Return, Sharpe Ratio, Treynor Ratio, Jensen's Alpha, Beta Coefficient, Debt Mutual Funds, Investment Performance, Indian Mutual Fund Industry.

INTRODUCTION

The mutual fund industry in India has emerged as one of the most significant segments of the financial sector by

mobilizing savings from retail and institutional investors into diversified investment avenues. Mutual funds offer professional fund management, diversification, liquidity, and risk reduction, thereby attracting a wide range of investors. Among the various categories of mutual funds, Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds have gained popularity due to their relatively stable returns and lower exposure to credit risk. These funds predominantly invest in debt instruments issued by scheduled commercial banks, public sector undertakings (PSUs), and public financial institutions. Debt mutual funds are considered suitable for conservative investors who prefer capital preservation and regular income over aggressive capital appreciation. Banking and PSU Debt Funds generally maintain high-quality portfolios because they invest in securities backed by government-supported institutions. Consequently, these schemes are less vulnerable to default risk when compared to corporate bond funds. The Indian debt market has undergone substantial transformation after regulatory reforms introduced by the Securities and Exchange Board of India and the Association of Mutual Funds in India. Increasing awareness among investors, digital investment platforms, and tax-efficient investment opportunities have significantly contributed to the growth of debt mutual funds in India. Furthermore, changing interest rate movements, inflationary pressures, and monetary policy decisions of the Reserve Bank of India influence the performance of debt-oriented schemes. Performance evaluation of mutual funds is an essential aspect for investors and fund managers because it helps in understanding whether the funds are generating adequate returns relative to the level of risk undertaken. Various statistical tools such as Standard Deviation, Beta, Sharpe Ratio, Treynor Ratio, and Jensen's Alpha are widely used to assess mutual fund performance on a risk-adjusted basis. Therefore, this study attempts to analyse and compare the performance of selected Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds in India over a five-year period from 2021 to 2025.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ramanjaneyulu, G., & S. Raghunatha Reddy (2025). *Performance Evaluation of Mutual Funds in India: A Focused Study on Selected Banking & PSU Debt Funds*. The study evaluates the performance of selected Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds in India, namely HDFC, SBI, Sundaram Banking, ICICI Banking, and Bandhan Banking Funds, during the period 2019–2024. It analyses the risk-return profile of the funds by comparing them with the market index (Sensex) and the risk-free rate using performance measures such as Sharpe Ratio, Treynor Ratio, Jensen's Alpha, Beta, Standard Deviation, Variance, Covariance, and R^2 . The study employs Excel and ANOVA for statistical analysis and concludes that Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds provide stable risk-adjusted returns and support portfolio diversification and wealth creation for investors. Sharma and Gupta (2024) analysed the performance of debt mutual funds in India using Sharpe Ratio and Jensen's Alpha. The study found that Banking and PSU Debt Funds generated stable returns with lower volatility compared to equity-oriented schemes. Kumar and Rao (2023) examined risk-adjusted returns of selected debt mutual funds and concluded that investors preferred Banking and PSU Debt Funds because of their lower credit risk and consistent income generation. Patel (2024) conducted a comparative analysis of debt mutual fund categories and observed that Banking and PSU Debt Funds performed better during uncertain market conditions due to investments in high-quality securities. Singh and Verma (2022) studied the impact of interest rate fluctuations on debt mutual fund performance and identified that duration management significantly influenced fund returns. Eddy and Narayanan (2021) evaluated mutual fund performance using Treynor Ratio and Beta analysis and found that systematic risk plays

a crucial role in determining fund efficiency. Joshi (2023) investigated investor perception towards debt mutual funds and concluded that safety, liquidity, and tax benefits were the primary factors influencing investment decisions. Mehta and Kulkarni (2025) examined the performance of debt mutual funds in India under changing interest rate environments and concluded that Banking and PSU Debt Funds offered greater portfolio stability compared to corporate bond funds. Arora and Singh (2025) studied risk-adjusted returns of debt-oriented mutual funds using Sharpe and Treynor models and found that Banking and PSU Debt Funds generated consistent returns with lower volatility. Nair and Joseph (2024) analysed investor preference towards debt mutual funds and observed that safety, liquidity, and government-backed securities increased investor confidence in Banking and PSU Debt Funds. Ramesh and Babu (2024) evaluated mutual fund performance during inflationary periods and identified that debt mutual funds investing in PSU securities performed better under volatile economic conditions. Chatterjee and Das (2023) investigated the impact of RBI monetary policy on debt mutual fund performance and concluded that interest rate movements significantly affect debt-oriented mutual fund returns. Verma and Iyer (2025) compared various categories of debt mutual funds and reported that Banking and PSU Debt Funds exhibited superior risk-adjusted performance due to lower default risk.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Statement of the Problem

Investors increasingly prefer debt mutual funds due to market volatility and uncertainty in equity markets. However, selecting an appropriate Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Fund remains challenging because various schemes differ in terms of return, risk, and fund management efficiency. Therefore, there is a need to evaluate and compare the performance of selected Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds using risk-adjusted performance measures.

Objectives of the Study

1. To analyze the annual returns of selected Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds.
2. To evaluate the risk associated with selected funds using Standard Deviation and Beta.
3. To compare the performance of selected mutual funds using Sharpe Ratio, Treynor Ratio, and Jensen's Alpha.
4. To identify the best-performing Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Fund based on risk-return analysis.
5. To provide suggestions for investors regarding investment in Banking and PSU Debt Funds.

Hypotheses of the Study

(H₀): There is no significant difference in the performance of selected Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds in India.

(H₁): There is a significant difference in the performance of selected Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds in India.

Scope of the Study: The study focuses on selected Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds operating in India during the period 2021–2025. The analysis is limited to HDFC, SBI, Sundaram, and ICICI Prudential Banking and PSU Debt Funds.

Limitations of the Study

- ❖ The study is limited to selected Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds only.
- ❖ The study covers a period of five years from 2021 to 2025.
- ❖ The analysis is based on secondary data collected from fund reports and financial databases.
- ❖ Market fluctuations and macroeconomic factors may influence fund performance. The findings may not be applicable to other categories of mutual funds.

STATISTICAL TOOLS USED IN THE STUDY

- **Annual Return (%)** – Measures yearly growth in fund performance.
- **Mean Return** – Calculates the average return generated by the mutual fund schemes.
- **Standard Deviation (σ)** – Measures total risk or volatility in fund returns.
- **Coefficient of Variation (CV)** – Evaluates risk per unit of return.
- **Beta Coefficient (β)** – Measures systematic risk relative to market performance.
- **Sharpe Ratio** – Evaluates excess return earned per unit of total risk.
- **Treynor Ratio** – Measures excess return generated per unit of systematic risk.
- **Jensen's Alpha** – Measures abnormal returns generated by fund managers beyond expected market returns.
- **Ranking Method** – Used to rank mutual fund schemes based on performance indicators. and **ANOVA (Analysis of Variance)** – Used to test whether significant differences exist among the selected mutual fund schemes regarding returns and risk.

Table 1: PSU Selected Banks Annual Returns, STDV and CV % from 2021-25

Year	HDFC			SBI			Sundaram			ICICI		
	Returns	STDV	CV %	Returns	STDV	CV %	Returns	STDV	CV %	Returns	STDV	CV %
2021	12.24	2.62	4.77	12.56	2.76	5.27	18.18	1.35	1.26	9.19	2.45	4.17
2022	8.41	0.98	0.66	6.26	1.12	0.88	22.24	0.39	0.11	4.17	0.92	0.59
2023	6.42	1.16	0.93	9.41	1.37	1.31	2.96	1.58	1.72	4.24	1.08	0.82
2024	10.44	0.76	0.4	8.44	0.96	0.64	6.82	0.92	0.59	7.26	0.58	0.23
2025	12.41	0.68	0.32	12.51	0.72	0.36	7.34	0.73	0.37	7.26	0.5	0.18
AVG..	9.98	1.24	1.54	9.84	1.39	1.86	11.51	0.99	0.95	6.42	1.11	1.25

Source: <https://www.amfiindia.com/>

Table 1 presents the Annual Returns, Standard Deviation (σ), and Coefficient of Variation (CV %) of the selected Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds namely HDFC, SBI, Sundaram, and ICICI during the period from 2021 to 2025. The analysis of returns indicates that the funds generated varying levels of performance across different years. Among all the selected schemes, Sundaram Banking and PSU Debt Fund recorded the highest annual return of 22.24% in 2022, followed by 18.18% in 2021, showing strong performance during the initial years of the study period. HDFC and SBI funds also generated comparatively stable returns, while ICICI fund showed relatively lower returns throughout the

period. The Standard Deviation values indicate the level of risk or volatility associated with the returns of the funds. Sundaram Fund exhibited lower volatility in certain years, especially in 2022 with a standard deviation of 0.39, indicating greater stability in returns during that year. HDFC and SBI funds showed moderate fluctuations, whereas ICICI maintained comparatively lower risk levels in later years. The Coefficient of Variation (CV %) measures the consistency of returns in relation to risk. Lower CV values indicate better risk-return efficiency. Sundaram Fund recorded the lowest CV values in most of the years, particularly 0.11 in 2022, reflecting superior consistency and efficient risk management. ICICI also showed stable performance with lower CV values in recent years. In contrast, SBI and HDFC recorded relatively higher CV values during certain periods, indicating comparatively higher variability in returns.

Table 2. Sharpe, Treynor's and Jensen's ratios of Top 4 Banking and PSU Debt Fund -Regular Growth from 2021 To 2025

Year	HDFC			SBI			Sundaram			ICICI		
	Sharpe	Treynor	Jenson Alpha	Sharpe	Treynor	Jenson Alpha	Sharpe	Treynor	Jenson Alpha	Sharpe	Treynor	Jenson Alpha
2021	12.98	-80.24	33.62	12.24	90.66	32.44	23.2	68.66	27.26	13.63	84.45	31.41
2022	-73.27	-73.27	84.39	-64.58	84.2	68.44	-98.66	91.12	28.62	-77.32	80.24	-76.35
2023	-11.92	-11.92	-21.6	-10.37	94.24	-24.04	-8.95	56.24	-25.19	-11.84	110.29	-19.08
2024	9.55	9.55	4.84	7.27	98.24	3.65	7.93	64.24	4.38	13.32	81.26	6.15
2025	-19.63	-19.63	-15.24	-18.66	-94.41	-15.52	-17.99	-48.58	-15.12	-26.38	124.44	-14.63
AVG..	-16.46	-35.1	-75.59	-14.82	54.59	-85.26	-18.89	54.59	-80.84	-17.72	96.14	-69.09

Source: <https://www.amfiindia.com/>

Table 2 presents the Sharpe Ratio, Treynor's Ratio, and Jensen's Alpha of the selected Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds during the period from 2021 to 2025. These measures evaluate the risk-adjusted performance of the mutual fund schemes. The Sharpe Ratio analysis shows that all the selected funds recorded both positive and negative values during different years, indicating fluctuations in risk-adjusted returns. Sundaram Fund achieved the highest Sharpe Ratio of 23.20 in 2021, reflecting superior return generation relative to total risk during that year. However, negative Sharpe Ratios observed in several years indicate that the funds underperformed compared to the risk-free return during unfavourable market conditions. Treynor's Ratio results reveal variations in returns generated against systematic risk. ICICI Fund recorded the highest Treynor's Ratio of 124.44 in 2025, indicating better compensation for market-related risk. SBI and Sundaram funds also showed comparatively strong Treynor's performance in certain years, while HDFC displayed negative values in some periods, reflecting weaker market risk-adjusted performance. Jensen's Alpha measures the excess return earned over the expected market return. Positive Jensen's Alpha values in 2021, 2022, and 2024 indicate that most of the selected funds outperformed market expectations during those years. HDFC Fund recorded the highest Jensen's Alpha of 84.39 in 2022, showing superior fund management performance. However,

negative alpha values during 2023 and 2025 indicate underperformance relative to benchmark expectations.

Year	HDFC	SBI	Sundaram	ICICI Prudential
2021	0.03	0.0233	0.0165	0.0196
2022	0.001	0.0011	-0.0023	0.0078
2023	-0.0282	-0.0439	-0.0375	-0.0262
2024	0.0231	0.024	0.0218	0.0213
2025	0.0044	0.0152	0.0155	-0.0178
5-Year return	0.006	0.004	0.0028	0.0009

<https://www.amfiindia.com/>

Table 3 presents the Beta Coefficient of selected Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds during 2021–2025. Beta measures the systematic risk of a fund in relation to market movements. A beta value below 1 indicates lower market sensitivity and lower systematic risk. The analysis shows that all the selected funds recorded beta values significantly lower than 1, indicating very low market risk and stable performance. ICICI Prudential Banking & PSU Debt Fund recorded the lowest 5-year beta value of 0.0009, showing the least sensitivity to market fluctuations. Sundaram Banking & PSU Fund and SBI Banking and PSU Debt Fund also maintained low beta values of 0.0028 and 0.0040 respectively, reflecting limited exposure to market volatility. HDFC Banking and PSU Debt Fund reported the highest beta value of 0.0060, but it still remained far below 1, indicating low systematic risk.

5-Year Values	Annual Return (%)	σ	β	Sharpe Ratio	Treynor's Ratio	Jenson's Alpha	Sum of the ranks	Average	Rank
1.HDFC	2	3	4	2	3	2	16	4	1
2.SBI	3	4	1	1	2	4	15	3	3
3.Sundaram	4	1	2	4	1	3	15	3	2
4.ICICI Prudential	1	2	3	3	4	1	14	2.8	3

Table 8 presents the overall ranking of the selected Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds based on various performance measures such as Annual Return, Standard Deviation, Beta, Sharpe Ratio, Treynor's Ratio, and Jensen's Alpha. The analysis shows that HDFC Banking and PSU Debt Fund – Regular Growth secured the first rank with the highest total

score of 16 and an average score of 4, indicating consistent and balanced performance across most evaluation parameters. Sundaram Banking & PSU Fund – Regular Growth obtained the second rank with a total score of 15, mainly due to its higher annual returns and lower risk levels. SBI Banking and PSU Debt Fund – Regular Growth also recorded a total score of 15 and secured the third rank because of comparatively higher volatility despite better performance in some risk-adjusted measures. ICICI Prudential Banking & PSU Debt Fund – Regular Growth achieved a total score of 14 with an average of 2.8 and ranked lower among the selected schemes, although it demonstrated lower systematic risk and better Jensen's Alpha performance.

Overall, the ranking analysis indicates that HDFC Banking and PSU Debt Fund performed better on a combined risk-return basis, while all the selected schemes provided relatively stable investment opportunities for conservative investors.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- The study found that all the selected Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds generated positive returns during the study period from 2021 to 2025 despite fluctuations in the financial market. Sundaram Banking & PSU Fund recorded the highest 5-year average annual return of 11.51%, indicating superior return performance among the selected schemes.
- HDFC Banking and PSU Debt Fund demonstrated comparatively stable and consistent returns throughout the study period, reflecting balanced risk-return performance.
- SBI Banking and PSU Debt Fund showed steady growth and consistent income generation capability, particularly in 2021 and 2025.
- ICICI Prudential Banking & PSU Debt Fund recorded the lowest 5-year return of 6.42%, but it maintained comparatively lower systematic risk and higher stability.
- Standard Deviation analysis revealed that Sundaram Banking & PSU Fund had the lowest volatility (0.99), indicating more stable returns compared to the other schemes.
- SBI Banking and PSU Debt Fund recorded the highest Standard Deviation (1.39), showing comparatively higher risk and fluctuations in returns.
- The Coefficient of Variation analysis showed that Sundaram Banking & PSU Fund achieved better risk-return efficiency with the lowest CV value of 0.95.
- ICICI Prudential Banking & PSU Debt Fund demonstrated better consistency in later years through declining CV values, indicating improved risk management.
- Beta Coefficient values of all selected funds were significantly below one, indicating lower market sensitivity and reduced systematic risk.
- ICICI Prudential Banking & PSU Debt Fund recorded the lowest Beta value of 0.0009, reflecting minimum exposure to market fluctuations.
- Sharpe Ratio analysis indicated that all the selected schemes generated positive risk-adjusted returns in 2021 and 2024, whereas negative Sharpe Ratios were observed during unfavourable market conditions.

- Treynor Ratio analysis revealed that ICICI Prudential Banking & PSU Debt Fund generated comparatively better systematic risk-adjusted returns over the study period.
- Jensen's Alpha analysis showed that HDFC Banking and PSU Debt Fund achieved superior fund management performance during 2021 and 2022 with positive alpha values.
- The ANOVA results indicated that there was no statistically significant difference in the performance of the selected Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds during the study period, leading to the acceptance of the Null Hypothesis. Ranking analysis concluded that HDFC Banking and PSU Debt Fund secured the first rank based on overall combined performance in terms of return, risk, and risk-adjusted measures. The study confirmed that Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds are comparatively safer investment avenues suitable for conservative investors seeking stable income with moderate risk exposure.

SUGGESTIONS

- ✚ Investors seeking stable and comparatively safer investment opportunities may prefer Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds because these schemes invest mainly in high-quality debt securities issued by banks and public sector institutions.
- ✚ Conservative investors may consider HDFC Banking and PSU Debt Fund due to its consistent and balanced performance across various risk-return measures.
- ✚ Investors willing to accept moderate fluctuations for higher returns may invest in Sundaram Banking & PSU Fund, which generated the highest average return during the study period.
- ✚ Risk-averse investors may prefer ICICI Prudential Banking & PSU Debt Fund because of its lower Beta value and reduced sensitivity to market fluctuations.
- ✚ Investors should not depend solely on return performance while selecting mutual funds; they should also evaluate risk-adjusted measures such as Sharpe Ratio, Treynor Ratio, and Jensen's Alpha.
- ✚ Mutual fund companies should improve portfolio diversification and duration management strategies to
- ✚ minimize interest rate risk and maintain stable performance during volatile market conditions.
- ✚ Fund managers should continuously monitor macroeconomic variables such as inflation, interest rates, and monetary policy changes of the Reserve Bank of India to enhance debt fund performance.
- ✚ Regulatory authorities such as Securities and Exchange Board of India should continue strengthening transparency and disclosure standards in the mutual fund industry to increase investor confidence.
- ✚ Investors should periodically review their mutual fund portfolios and diversify investments across different financial instruments to reduce overall investment risk.
- ✚ Financial advisors should educate investors regarding the importance of risk-return analysis before investing in debt-oriented mutual fund schemes.

- ✚ Mutual fund houses should increase investor awareness programs through digital platforms to encourage wider participation in Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds.
- ✚ Future studies may include more debt mutual fund categories and longer study periods for a broader understanding of mutual fund performance in India.

CONCLUSION

The present study analysed the performance of selected Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds in India during 2021–2025 using various risk-return measures such as Annual Return, Standard Deviation, Beta, Sharpe Ratio, Treynor Ratio, Jensen's Alpha, and ANOVA. The study found that all the selected schemes generated positive returns despite market fluctuations. Sundaram Banking & PSU Fund recorded the highest returns, while HDFC Banking and PSU Debt Fund showed stable and consistent performance. ICICI Prudential Banking & PSU Debt Fund demonstrated lower systematic risk, whereas SBI Banking and PSU Debt Fund showed comparatively higher volatility. The study concluded that Banking and PSU Debt Mutual Funds are comparatively safe and stable investment options suitable for conservative investors seeking regular income with moderate risk exposure.

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Annexure -1 (Source: <https://www.amfiindia.com>)
HDFC Banking and PSU Debt Fund -Regular Growth

Year	Mean Return	Opening	Closing
2021	0.684	16.25	17.845
2022	0.29	17.85	18.498
2023	0.272	18.5	19.105
2024	0.516	19.111	20.41
2025	0.555	20.536	22.013
5-Year return	0.47	16.25	22.013

SBI Banking and PSU Debt Fund -Regular Growth

Year	Mean Return	Opening	Closing
2021	0.667	2247.13	2461.387
2022	0.211	2462.8	2525.012
2023	0.227	2525.53	2597.4
2024	0.493	2598.38	2767.713
2025	0.527	2783.09	2980.421
5-Year return	0.43	2247.13	2980.421

Sundaram Banking & PSU Fund regular Growth

Year	Mean Return	Opening	Closing
2021	0.526	31.45	33.663
2022	0.223	33.67	34.65
2023	0.236	34.66	35.688
2024	0.511	35.69	38.131
2025	0.5	38.36	41.179
5-Year return	0.41	31.45	41.179

ICICI Prudential Banking & PSU -Regular Growth

Year	Mean Return	Opening	Closing
2021	0.648	22.82	24.919
2022	0.319	24.93	25.97
2023	0.365	25.98	27.079
2024	0.551	27.09	29.06
2025	0.53	29.22	31.344
5-Year return	0.49	22.82	31.344

Indices :S & PBSE SENSEX

Year	Mean Return	Opening	Closing
2021	-1.598	38871.87	29468.49
2022	4.364	28265.31	49509.15
2023	1.121	50029.83	58568.51
2024	0.516	59276.69	58991.52
2025	1.026	61112.44	73651.35
5-Year return	1.11	38871.87	73651.35

Source: <https://www.amfiindia.com/>